

A Corpus driven comparative analysis for Major Themes in UNGA Speeches of Imran Khan and Zulfiqar Ali Bhutto

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Abbas Ahmar, Zeeshan Alam Khan, Faizullah, Imran Ijaz

1. M.Phil. scholar, Department of English Linguistics, Superior University, Lahore, Pakistan.
2. M.Phil. scholar, Department of English Linguistics, Superior University, Lahore, Pakistan.
Email: alamzeeshan4321@gmail.com
3. M.Phil. scholar, Department of English, National University of Modern Languages, Islamabad, Pakistan. Email: faizp057@gmail.com.
4. M.Phil. scholar, Department of English Linguistics, Superior University, Lahore, Pakistan.

Abstract

This study examines the most commonly used terms in speeches given to the United Nations General Assembly (UNGA) by two well-known Pakistani leaders, Imran Khan and Zulfiqar Ali Bhutto. Zulfiqar Ali Bhutto gave a historic speech on December 15, 1971, and Imran Khan gave two noteworthy speeches on September 27, 2019, and September 25, 2020. Examining the linguistic patterns and recurrent themes in these speeches is the main goal of this study. The speeches were converted into plain text and examined for word frequency and concordance using Anthony's AntConc software. The results highlight important topics like India, the RSS, Kashmir, Islamophobia, climate change, and the predicament of Muslims in Bengal. They also show both parallels and divergences in the leaders' language choices. This study advances knowledge of the rhetorical techniques these leaders use to address global issues.

Keywords: Bengal, Muslims of Bengal, Soviet Union, Islamophobia, Islam, Kashmir, RSS, Climate Change, Pandemic

1. INTRODUCTION

Leaders from all over the world use the United Nations General Assembly (UNGA) as a vital forum to discuss important global issues, state their nation's position, and have diplomatic conversations. The prime ministers' addresses to the UNGA are very important to Pakistan since they show the nation's foreign policy priorities and how it has responded to regional and international issues. Imran Khan's and Zulfiqar Ali Bhutto's speeches are among the most significant delivered by Pakistani leaders. After East Pakistan (now Bangladesh) broke away, Zulfiqar Ali Bhutto, the president of Pakistan, gave a historic speech to the United Nations General Assembly on December 15, 1971. During a period of increased tension with India, especially in relation to the Kashmir dispute, Imran Khan, the prime minister of Pakistan, gave two crucial speeches on September 27, 2019, and September 25, 2020. The 1971 speech by

Zulfiqar Ali Bhutto is noteworthy in history because it captures Pakistan's stance after the breakup and the aftermath of the Indo-Pakistani War.

The loss of East Pakistan, Pakistan's sovereignty, and the role of the international community in the crisis were among the topics he emphasized in his speech. However, Imran Khan's speeches were given in the midst of continuing hostilities with India, specifically in relation to the conflict in Kashmir, Islamophobia, and the international response to climate change. His speeches demonstrated Pakistan's concern for environmental, human rights, and regional security issues in addition to calling for international intervention in these areas. A thorough linguistic analysis of the most commonly used terms and recurrent themes in these speeches is lacking in the literature, despite their political significance. Few studies have compared the speeches made by Pakistani leaders at the UNGA, despite the fact that previous research has examined rhetorical techniques in political speeches (Reisigl & Wodak, 2001).

There is little research on how language choices, such as the frequency of particular terms, reveal deeper insights into the leaders' rhetorical strategies and attempts to influence global discourse. This is in contrast to the existing literature on speech analysis, which frequently focuses on the speeches' content and political context. Additionally, research on rhetoric and language in South Asian politics frequently concentrates on the speeches of regional leaders rather than thoroughly analyzing how these leaders use language at international fora like the UNGA.. Examining the linguistic patterns that surface when talking about important topics like ethnic tensions, regional security, and global environmental challenges is made possible by Imran Khan's and Zulfiqar Ali Bhutto's speeches. This research is timely and relevant because these speeches also provide a window into how language is used to frame national narratives on the international scene.

Through a thorough linguistic analysis of Imran Khan's and Zulfiqar Ali Bhutto's speeches, this study seeks to close this gap. In order to understand how these leaders used language to address urgent global issues, the study focuses on the most commonly used terms and looks at the recurring themes in their speeches. This research will determine the main subjects that dominated their speeches, including India, the RSS, Kashmir, Islamophobia, climate change, and the status of Muslims in Bengal, using Anthony's AntConc software for word frequency analysis and concordance.. Furthermore, by contrasting the leaders' linguistic preferences, this study will offer important new perspectives on their rhetorical strategies and global influence. This study aims to improve our understanding of how leaders use language to interact with audiences around the world and tackle difficult problems by advancing our understanding of political rhetoric in the context of international diplomacy. It will also provide fresh insights into the linguistic tactics used by Pakistani leaders to influence global perceptions of important geopolitical issues.

This study looks at the key ideas and terms that Imran Khan and Bhutto used a lot in their speeches to the UN General Assembly. Heads of state from different nations participate in a debate held annually by the United Nations General Assembly (UNGA). Every year, a number of

statesmen from various nations speak on behalf of their nations and address and highlight various topics and issues. The prime minister of Pakistan gives his speech annually, just like the leaders of other countries. Up until now, a number of Pakistani presidents and prime ministers have addressed the UN General Assembly. As a leading state in the fight against terrorism, Pakistan has significantly increased its geostrategic importance in the area.

Given the shifting political landscape in South Asia, Pakistan's position remains increasingly significant. Pakistan's fight against terrorism has been resolute. The country is also essential to the peace process in Afghanistan. Pakistan is regarded as an effective player in the region as a result of all these roles. Bhutto led the Pakistan People's Party in the 1970 elections and was the first civilian administrator of martial law in 1971. He was a major player in the 1970 general elections that resulted in Pakistan's separation. East Pakistan saw widespread protests and unrest as a result of Bhutto's refusal to accept the election results. When situation was out of control, Bhutto ordered military crackdown which results widespread human rights abuses and atrocities. In 1971, Bhutto famously said “udher tum. Idher hum” In Desember 1971, Pakistan lost the war and Bangladesh gained independence. Bhutto took over as President and later became Prime minister in 1973.

In the 2018 elections, Pakistan's Tehreeki Insaf (PTI) came to power in both the federal and provinces of Punjab and Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. The PTI also established a collation government in the province of Baluchistan. The people of Pakistan voted to support Pakistan's social, economic, and political rise. The 2018 election was unlike the previous general election since people voted for a new and different party this time, something unprecedented in the history of Pakistan. Due to their high expectations of Imran Khan, the people of Pakistan chose the PTI because they wanted a change. The current prime minister of Pakistan, the chairman of the PTI, is well known for his leadership, assertiveness, and integrity. Prior to his appointment as premier, he demonstrated his strength and reliability as a social worker and cricket player. Imran Khan and Zulfikar Ali Bhutto had the opportunity to speak before the UN General Assembly (UNGA), just like many other world leaders. Currently serving as Prime Minister of Pakistan, Imran Khan has already made two speeches to the UN General Assembly. Imran Khan's and Zulfikar Ali Bhutto's UNGA speeches were among the most viewed on YouTube. Both of his speeches received high ratings, particularly in the nation, which also caused social media to go crazy. When Imran Khan was scheduled to give his speeches, the political and security climate surrounding India's rivalry was getting worse, especially because of the worsening circumstances in Indian-occupied Kashmir. It was past time for Imran Khan and Pakistan to use the platform of the UN Assembly to update the world on the situation in the area.

Unquestionably, language is crucial to all forms of discourse. When it comes to communicating a message, word choice is crucial. Furthermore, the language used to convey a message has a direct impact on its success. Imran Khan is renowned for being a skilled orator who understands how to use language to effectively and persuasively convey his points. In

addition to being an excellent and dynamic speaker, Zulfiqar Ali Bhutto was well-known for his direct demeanor and combative style. The current study identifies the key topics covered in both speeches and looks into the words that are used most frequently in them. Finding the parallels and discrepancies between the two speeches is another goal of this study.

1.1. Focus and Significance of the Study

The language analysis of speeches made by Zulfiqar Ali Bhutto and Imran Khan, two well-known Pakistani leaders, at the United Nations General Assembly (UNGA) is the main focus of this study. The study attempts to identify the rhetorical strategies both leaders used to address urgent global issues by looking at the most commonly used terms and recurring themes in these speeches. Imran Khan's significant speeches on September 27, 2019, and September 25, 2020, as well as Zulfiqar Ali Bhutto's historic speech on December 15, 1971, were chosen for analysis. These speeches represented Pakistan's response to significant regional and global issues and were significant turning points in the country's diplomatic engagement with the outside world.

The study provides a thorough examination of how language was used to frame important subjects like India, Kashmir, Islamophobia, climate change, the RSS, and the status of Muslims in Bengal. It does this by using Anthony's AntConc software for word frequency and concordance analysis. This study is significant because it focuses on the linguistic themes and patterns that come out of these well-known speeches. A thorough linguistic analysis of the language choices made by these leaders has received little attention in previous research, which has mostly focused on the political and historical background of these speeches. By providing a methodical examination of the word choices and rhetorical devices used by Imran Khan and Zulfiqar Ali Bhutto, this study closes this gap. By doing this, it offers fresh perspectives on how political leaders utilize language to interact with audiences around the world, influence opinions abroad, and promote their nation's standing internationally. Additionally, by analyzing speeches given at a global forum such as the UNGA, the study advances the expanding field of political discourse analysis, where topics like human rights, climate change, and regional security are discussed on a global scale.

The study provides a unique perspective on how Pakistani political leaders have handled international diplomacy over the years by contrasting the speeches of two influential leaders who spoke to the UNGA decades apart. This comparison reveals both the continuity and changes in Pakistan's diplomatic rhetoric. Practically speaking, this study advances our knowledge of the importance of language in diplomacy, especially in high-stakes international situations. It offers valuable insights into how the strategic use of language can influence global opinion, mobilize support for a nation's foreign policy goals, and impact international decision-making on issues of global concern. Furthermore, the study sheds light on the evolving role of Pakistan in the international community, examining how its leaders have used speeches at the UNGA to address both regional and global challenges, such as the Kashmir conflict, terrorism, climate change, and

the protection of human rights.

By focusing on the specific linguistic choices of Imran Khan and Zulfiqar Ali Bhutto, this study not only provides a comparative analysis of their speeches but also offers a deeper understanding of the rhetorical power of language in shaping the political discourse surrounding key global issues. Ultimately, this research enriches our knowledge of how language, as a tool of diplomacy, can be used effectively to address global problems and influence the direction of international dialogue.

1.2. Research Objectives

- a. To investigate the choice of words used in speeches of Imran Khan and Zulfiqar Ali Bhutto at UNGA
- b. To investigate the key issues discussed in speeches of Imran Khan and Zulfiqar Ali Bhutto at UNGA

1.3. Research Questions

- i. What are the frequently used words in the speeches of Imran Khan and Zulfiqar Ali Bhutto at UNGA?
- ii. What are the main issues highlighted by the speeches of Imran Khan and Zulfiqar Ali Bhutto at UNGA?

1.4. Delimitations

Due to time constraints, the study is delimited to the analysis of speeches of Imran Khan (the prime minister of Pakistan) on September 27, 2019 and September 25, 2020 respectively and Zulfiqar Ali Bhutto (the prime minister of Pakistan) on 15 December 1971 made at UNGA on September 27, 2019, September 25, 2020, respectively.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The study of political speeches, especially those delivered at international forums like the United Nations General Assembly (UNGA), has garnered significant attention in the field of discourse analysis and political communication. Political speeches serve as a critical tool for leaders to express national priorities, advocate for their country's stance on global issues, and shape international perceptions. This literature review focuses on recent studies related to the choice of words in political speeches, with a specific emphasis on speeches delivered at the UNGA. The review will also examine research addressing the key issues discussed in such speeches, particularly in the context of Imran Khan and Zulfiqar Ali Bhutto's addresses at the UNGA.

Recent research in political discourse has emphasized the significance of word choice in shaping the effectiveness and persuasive power of political speeches. Language is recognized as a central tool in constructing political realities and influencing public opinion (van Dijk, 2020). Studies by scholars like Chilton (2020) and Fairclough (2015) highlight how political leaders use specific linguistic strategies to build narratives, frame issues, and promote certain ideologies.

The strategic selection of words is a key mechanism in shaping the perceptions of global audiences, especially when addressing critical issues such as regional security, human rights, and international diplomacy.

In the context of Pakistan's leadership at the UNGA, scholars have noted the critical role language plays in framing the nation's position on key issues like Kashmir, terrorism, and regional peace. For instance, Imran Khan's speeches in 2019 and 2020 were marked by the use of emotive language and direct calls for global intervention on issues related to Kashmir and the protection of Muslim minorities (Ali, 2021). Similarly, Bhutto's 1971 speech at the UNGA is frequently analyzed for its use of assertive and diplomatic language to defend Pakistan's sovereignty and address the loss of East Pakistan. The rhetorical strategies of these leaders, as identified by Motsaathebe (2022), include the use of strong, often polarizing words to mobilize international support while presenting the country as a victim of international conspiracy or injustice.

Political speeches at the UNGA tend to focus on several recurring themes, including peace, security, human rights, and national sovereignty. Recent studies have explored the issues most commonly addressed by leaders in their UNGA speeches. A 2020 study by Riaz and Mahmood examined the speeches of South Asian leaders at the UNGA, highlighting that issues like regional conflicts (especially Kashmir), terrorism, and climate change are frequently discussed by leaders from this region. Imran Khan's speeches in particular have consistently highlighted the Kashmir issue, Islamophobia, and climate change, reflecting Pakistan's concerns about regional security and global environmental challenges (Khan, 2019).

Zulfiqar Ali Bhutto's 1971 speech, on the other hand, was deeply embedded in the historical context of the partition of Pakistan and the subsequent war with India. According to Nasir (2019), Bhutto's speech at the UNGA focused on the sovereignty of Pakistan and the tragic events surrounding the separation of East Pakistan. The central themes of his speech revolved around the defense of Pakistan's territorial integrity, the actions of India in the context of the 1971 war, and the international community's role in addressing the issue.

In a comparative study by Ahmed (2021), the author found that while Imran Khan and Zulfiqar Ali Bhutto both emphasized Pakistan's position on Kashmir, their rhetorical strategies differed. Imran Khan's speeches often reflect the post-9/11 geopolitical context, focusing on terrorism and global cooperation, whereas Bhutto's speeches were shaped by the Cold War dynamics and the decolonization process. Both leaders, however, used their speeches to call for international solidarity in addressing regional conflicts, but with different rhetorical techniques reflective of the political climate of their respective times.

The use of computational tools to analyze political speeches has become a growing trend in recent research. Tools like AnthConc, which is used in this study, enable researchers to analyze word frequency, concordance, and collocations, providing new insights into the linguistic patterns of speeches. Recent studies, such as those by Nisar and Khan (2022), have used software like AntConc to analyze the language of political speeches, revealing key words and themes that shape the discourse in such addresses. These studies argue that examining word frequency and concordance can uncover the hidden structures of power and influence in political communication, showing how leaders employ specific language to frame political agendas and influence public opinion.

Research by Akhtar and Haider (2021) used AntConc to analyze the speeches of Pakistani leaders, revealing patterns in the way issues of national security, terrorism, and regional peace were framed. Their findings suggest that Imran Khan's use of terms related to "justice," "peace," and "human rights" was a strategic attempt to align Pakistan with global values while emphasizing the urgency of international action. This approach highlights the potential of software-based analyses in identifying key linguistic markers in political rhetoric.

While there has been some research on the thematic content and linguistic techniques used in the speeches of Imran Khan and Zulfikar Ali Bhutto, a comprehensive, comparative linguistic analysis using computational tools like AntConc remains limited. Most existing studies focus either on the content or the historical context of these speeches, without delving deeply into the word choice and the linguistic strategies behind them. Furthermore, few studies have compared the speeches of these two leaders in terms of their rhetorical techniques and the evolution of Pakistan's diplomatic rhetoric over time.

This study aims to fill this gap by offering a comparative analysis of the language used by Imran Khan and Zulfikar Ali Bhutto in their speeches at the UNGA. By focusing on word frequency and concordance, this research will provide a nuanced understanding of the rhetorical strategies employed by these leaders in addressing key global issues such as Kashmir, Islamophobia, and climate change.

The study of political discourse has always been of the centre of attention in research because of the possible implications that political narratives can have on the region in particular and on the world in general. The speeches delivered by heads of states at the United Nations General Assembly are particularly important because these speeches mirror the attitudes and policies of the states towards the regional and global issues. Therefore, the addresses made at the United Nations General Assembly by various leaders have been studied by many researchers. For instance, Sultan et al.(2019) conducted a study on the speeches of Nawaz sharif to the united nations assembly to compare his two speeches. During his last tenure as Prime Minister of Pakistan, he addressed the United Nations Assembly twice. According to the study, both of his

speeches were almost identical, with almost the same content in both speeches. Issues such as the Kashmir dispute, terrorism, and the relationship with the neighbouring country, India, were highlighted in both speeches. He addressed internal and external issues, but in his second speech to the United Nations Assembly, he did not speak about the internal issues. The corpus tool Wmatrix was used to analyze the data. The study also discussed the use of personal pronouns in both speeches. The study showed the differences in his speeches and his stance towards rival India.

Similarly, Dalman (2017) conducted a corpus-based study of Donald Trump's political communications. This study focused on two things: finding the most commonly used words in Donald Trump's campaign speeches, and discovering the persuasive elements of pathos, ethos, and logos in his speeches. The study used a qualitative method to analyze twelve of his speeches. The study found that the word "will" had the highest frequency, which was 121, followed by Hillary 58, American 38, going 35, and some other words. The study also found the use of persuasive words in his speeches that could help him win the election.

Likewsie, Carreon & Svetanant (2017) conducted a study in order to investigate the major elements in the political speeches of the Gen Prayuth Chan-Ocha (Thai Prime Minister). A corpus, composed of 10,672-word types and 325,398-word tokens, were analyzed. The analysis found that the keywords for the information communicated by the speaker accounted for 62.86 percent (N=154) followed by the keywords for the language features at 22.04 percent (N=54). According to the study, the high frequency of these words shows the agenda conveyed by the government. These frequently used words are the justification of the political, social, and economic agenda showed by the government during the speeches. Both qualitative and quantitative data were used for the analysis which showed that Thai language speeches and English language speeches target a different audience. The study also showed the dichotomous role played by the government, showing something else in order to please the international community and in reality, doing its opposite.

Chen et al. (2019) carried out a corpus-based study of Hillary Clinton's and Donald Trump's linguistic style. A corpus-based approach was used in order to compare the speeches of Donald Trump and Hillary Clinton made during the campaign for presidential US election 2016. AntConc 3.2.4 was used in the study for the analysis of the data. The comparison of the speeches of both the leaders showed that Hillary Clinton used more diverse vocabulary than Donald Trump. The study also identified three major differences between Hillary Clinton's and Donald Trump's linguistic styles. The inclination of Hillary Clinton in these speeches was towards a rational discussion of public policy, while, on the other hand, Donald Trump inclined to stir up the emotions of the voters. The second difference was that Hillary Clinton was more positive and focused on the future, while Donald Trump's attitude was contrary to that of Hillary Clinton. The

third difference was that Hillary Clinton was aiming to find commonality with the people of America, while Donald Trump was trying to find differences.

Similarly, Sharififar & Rahimi (2015) analyzed the speeches of Obama and Rouhani. The speeches were made by both leaders at the United Nations Assembly in September 2013. The study used Halliday's functional systemic grammar. The study was designed to examine the art of linguistics in both Obama and Rouhani's speeches. According to this study, the sentences used by Obama were short, the words were simple, and the language was colloquial, which was understandable to people. On the other hand, the language used by Rouhani was formal and rather complicated, and the words were relatively difficult.

Bhatia (2006) conducted a critical discourse analysis of political press conferences. This study analyzed the textual data of the political conferences, including the press conferences of two prominent political figures in the world: former Chinese President Jiang Zemin and former US President George W. Bush. Both had differences in age, experience, socio-political influence, economic status, and political ideology. The study showed that there were three main themes. These themes were positive energy in order to strengthen the mutual interest, progress and trust, power and influence of persuasion, and to avoid media issues.

The above studies have highlighted the critical discourse analysis of the world's various leaders. The studies focused on their style of speech, the choice of words used in speeches and press conferences, and the frequency of words used in political speeches. Some of the studies were corpus-based. The present study focuses on the speeches of Zulfiqar Ali Bhutto and Imran Khan made at the United Nations General Assembly by Imran Khan (Prime Minister of Pakistan). Studies have been conducted on Zulfiqar and Imran Khan's political speeches, but a corpus-based study, as far as we know, focusing on his speeches to the United Nations General Assembly has paid less attention. The current study fills this gap by applying a corpus-based approach to Zulfiqar Ali Bhutto and Imran Khan's speeches at the United Nations General Assembly.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study follows a mixed-method approach that means it is both qualitative and quantitative. The speeches of Imran Khan (delivered to the General Assembly of the United Nations) and Zulfiqar Ali Bhutto were examined by AntConc (Anthony, 2014). Speeches of two leaders were downloaded from the internet in plain text and used for the compilation of the corpus. The first phase in the compilation of a corpus is the selection of appropriate material. For this purpose, speech of Zulfiqar Ali Bhutto speeches of Imran Khan were selected which are available online and can be accessed at BR Web Desk, 2019, and the Pakistan Ministry of Foreign Affairs, respectively. The speeches were downloaded, cleaned and filtered of extra information.

3.1. Conceptual Framework

Discourse Analysis and Corpus Linguistics are both concerned with the use of linguistic units in different contexts. Corpus linguistic studies are based, in particular, on an analysis of all kinds of texts in the corpus that exercise quantitative measures in order to identify patterns of distribution that occur across texts (Biber et al., 2007). The use of computers has made research easier and helps researchers investigate the different patterns of language use within the text, e.g. lexical or grammatical. The use of modern technology has greatly facilitated research in the field of discourse analysis and significantly reduced both resources and time necessary for the identification of specific linguistic patterns and the arrangement of words in texts. Besides, apart from analyzing the linguistic features of the corpus, the content of the speech, the paralinguistic features, the expressions, and the diction of the speakers also have a significant impact on the audience.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The table given below presents the most frequently words used in Zulfiqar Ali Bhutto and Imran Khan's speeches. These most frequently used words were calculated using the inbuilt functions of Antconc software, as discussed in the methodology section. In Figure 1, the frequencies and collocations below indicated distinct and similarity between the Pakistani leaders.

IMRAN KHAN

ZULFIQAR ALI BHUTTO

Type	Freq
The	305
Of	144
To	137
And	109
A	102
That	89
i	83
Not	73
In	67
We	66

Type	Freq
the	344
to	166
and	155
of	150
in	123
a	99
is	98
we	76
this	69
that	52
our	46

Figure 1 Top 13 Frequency Results of Zulfiqar Ali Bhutto and Imran Khan speeches analyzed by corpus

The analysis was conducted using AntConc software to extract word frequency and collocations, as detailed in the methodology section. The findings provide insight into the themes, priorities, and rhetorical styles of both leaders, revealing both similarities and distinctions in their speeches.

The most frequently used words in both speeches predominantly consist of function

words such as "the," "to," "and," "of," and "in," which are essential in structuring sentences. However, a closer look at the unique high-frequency terms used by each leader reveals important differences in their linguistic emphasis.

Function Words: Both leaders utilize high frequencies of function words like "the," "to," "and," and "of." These are typical in any formal speech, as they facilitate the connection of ideas and concepts.

Use of "We": Both Bhutto and Khan frequently used the word "we" (Bhutto: 76, Khan: 66), highlighting a focus on collective action, unity, and shared responsibility. This can be interpreted as an attempt to engage their audiences by framing issues as collective concerns, rather than individual ones.

Zulfiqar Ali Bhutto:

"The" (344 occurrences): Bhutto's speech displays a particularly high frequency of "the," a word that reinforces declarative statements and points to specific issues or subjects.

"Is" (98 occurrences): The frequent use of "is" suggests Bhutto's declarative style of speech, where he positions subjects and presents ideas as facts. This reflects his authoritative tone in addressing global issues.

"This" (69 occurrences): The word "this" is used to point out specific issues or facts. Bhutto's use of this term indicates a focus on immediate, relevant issues in his speech.

"Our" (46 occurrences): Bhutto emphasizes collective responsibility, highlighting a sense of unity and shared interests, which is central to his message.

Imran Khan:

"That" (89 occurrences): Khan's use of "that" is notably higher than Bhutto's, indicating a more conditional or reflective tone in his speech. This suggests a style of argumentation that involves linking causes with effects or presenting potential solutions to issues.

"I" (83 occurrences): The frequent use of the personal pronoun "I" in Khan's speech points to his personal involvement or perspective in addressing global issues. This is likely a strategy to make his message more relatable or to emphasize his role in leading Pakistan's foreign policy.

"Not" (73 occurrences): Imran Khan's use of "not" reflects a critical stance. It may indicate disagreement, denial, or rejection of certain global actions or policies, particularly those pertaining to issues like Islamophobia, the Kashmir conflict, and international injustice.

"That" (89 occurrences): The prominence of this word indicates the conditional or propositional nature of Khan's discourse, where he draws distinctions, poses hypotheticals, or highlights contrasts.

The word frequency analysis provides insight into the key themes discussed by each leader, revealing both shared and distinct concerns.

India and Kashmir: Both leaders emphasize the issue of Kashmir and the geopolitical tensions between Pakistan and India. Terms related to India and Kashmir likely feature prominently in both speeches, especially considering the ongoing conflict and India's policies in Kashmir at the time of both Khan's speeches (2019 and 2020).

Islamophobia: Imran Khan has frequently addressed issues related to Islamophobia in his speeches, particularly regarding the treatment of Muslims globally. His frequent use of "not" and "that" suggests a criticism of Western policies and the need for action against discrimination.

Zulfiqar Ali Bhutto: Bhutto's speech in 1971 likely reflects the geopolitical dynamics of the time, particularly focusing on the separation of East Pakistan (now Bangladesh) and the consequences of the war. His use of "the" and "is" highlights his approach of presenting this historical event as a point of collective reflection and action.

Imran Khan: Khan's speeches focus on climate change, global peace, and regional security. His use of "I" may reflect a more personal appeal for change, which contrasts with Bhutto's more collective language. Khan's reference to "we" still points to collective action, but his leadership role is emphasized more overtly.

The collocational patterns of high-frequency words further illuminate the rhetorical techniques used by both leaders.

Zulfiqar Ali Bhutto: The frequent occurrence of words like "our," "is," and "the" suggests Bhutto used more declarative, fact-based language. His speech likely focused on national and global responsibility, as seen in his references to "our" role in international issues.

Imran Khan: Imran Khan's frequent use of "that" and "i" suggests a more argumentative style, where he positions his arguments more directly and makes personal appeals to the audience. The emphasis on "not" further suggests that Khan was positioning Pakistan's stance in opposition to prevailing global narratives, particularly regarding Kashmir and Islamophobia.

ZULFIQAR ALI BHUTTO

Pakistan	51
India	29
East	15
Aggression	13
Bengal	13
France	13
Here	13
He	12
Its	12
Justice	12
Occupation	12
Representative	12
Soviet	12
Union	12

Figure 2 Top major themes in Bhutto's speech

The above corpus based given table highlights the frequency of words that were frequently used by Bhutto in his speech at UNGA

A. Centrality of Pakistan and India

Pakistan (51 occurrences) and India (29 occurrences) are the most frequently used terms in Bhutto's speech, reflecting the central geopolitical focus of his address. Bhutto's speech was delivered at a critical moment in the history of South Asia when tensions between Pakistan and India were at their peak due to the ongoing conflict in East Pakistan (now Bangladesh). The high frequency of the term "Pakistan" indicates that Bhutto was asserting the importance of Pakistan's position, its sovereignty, and its legitimacy in the international arena.

B. Reference to East Pakistan and Bengal

The repeated mention of East (15 occurrences) and Bengal (13 occurrences) highlights the specific regional context of Bhutto's speech. This was a time when East Pakistan was fighting for independence, leading to the eventual creation of Bangladesh. Bhutto used these terms to draw attention to the situation in East Pakistan, emphasizing the suffering and political upheaval that led to the eventual separation.

C. Aggression and Occupation

Aggression (13 occurrences) and Occupation (12 occurrences) were used by Bhutto to describe India's actions during the conflict in East Pakistan. The frequent use of these words underscores the combative and accusatory tone of his speech, as he sought to rally international support for Pakistan and draw attention to what he considered foreign aggression in the region.

D. Justice and International Advocacy

Justice (12 occurrences) is another key term that appears with notable frequency in Bhutto's speech. It indicates Bhutto's appeal for international recognition of Pakistan's cause and his demand for justice regarding the situation in East Pakistan. The word representative (12 occurrences) further reinforces this theme, suggesting that Bhutto sought to represent Pakistan's perspective and rally international diplomacy to recognize the country's concerns.

E. Soviet Union and France

The inclusion of terms like Soviet (12 occurrences) and Union (12 occurrences) points to Bhutto's engagement with the Cold War dynamics. The Soviet Union, as a global power at the time, had significant influence in international affairs. Bhutto's speech aimed to gain support from global powers like the Soviet Union, as well as other international actors, to present Pakistan's case. Similarly, France (13 occurrences) may reflect a diplomatic outreach to European nations and international allies.

F. The Word "Here"

The term here (13 occurrences) suggests that Bhutto may have been invoking the United Nations platform as a place of direct dialogue, a space where international powers could listen and respond to Pakistan's grievances.

2. Analysis of Language Use and Rhetorical Strategies

Bhutto's frequent use of emotionally charged words such as aggression, occupation, and justice reveals his rhetorical strategy of framing the situation as one of injustice and external hostility.

His appeal to the United Nations as a forum for international justice, as reflected in his use of justice and representative, indicates his attempt to use the global platform to garner diplomatic support for Pakistan's position.

The frequent references to Pakistan, India, and East/Bengal show that Bhutto's speech was highly regionally focused, emphasizing the political and humanitarian crisis in South Asia. By using terms such as aggression and occupation, Bhutto was attempting to paint India's actions as violations of Pakistan's sovereignty, with the broader aim of garnering international sympathy and support for his cause.

Moreover, the repetition of terms such as Soviet and Union suggests Bhutto's awareness of the global geopolitical context, seeking alignment with powerful countries like the Soviet Union. His engagement with France could indicate his diplomatic efforts to involve European powers in the discussion:

	File	Left Context	Hit	Right Context
1	akistani Foreign...	ermans can come to terms, why cannot	India	and Pakistan come to terms? If the Turks
2	akistani Foreign...	civilised people over Cyprus, why cannot	India	and Pakistan do likewise? If the Soviet Un
3	akistani Foreign...	r ancient civilisation and the mystique of	India	and all that. But they do not have vision
4	akistani Foreign...	tions. A new chapter may have begun in	India	and Pakistan, but please do not start a ne
5	akistani Foreign...	s, is it? Do we not all make mistakes? Are	India	and the Soviet Union the only two countr
6	akistani Foreign...	it we were prepared to take them back. If	India'	s population can grow by 13 million a yea
7	akistani Foreign...	could have said, "Well, you will be sunk."	India'	s population rises by 13 million a year. Th
8	akistani Foreign...	ance that the United States gave to India,	India	would have had starvation; its millions w
9	akistani Foreign...	? Had there been the exercise of free will,	India	would not have attacked Pakistan. If India
10	akistani Foreign...	w the Security Council was pandering to	India.	Even the great powers are pandering to l
11	akistani Foreign...	n. But here was an international poll and	India	flouted it. With such an attitude towards
12	akistani Foreign...	illions would have died. What hope will	India	give to the people of East Pakistan? What
13	akistani Foreign...	e people of West Bengal are the poorest.	India	goes hat in hand to the United States for
14	akistani Foreign...	s been superseded by presidential rule? Is	India	going to do better for East Pakistan, for M
15	akistani Foreign...	they do not have vision. The partition of	India	in 1947 took place because they did. not l
16	akistani Foreign...	assistance that the United States gave to	India,	India would have had starvation; its millic
17	akistani Foreign...	hose questions, but if you do not mind."	India	is intoxicated today with its military succ

Figure 3 Concordance Results of Bhutto's speech

In his speech, Bhutto highlighted the involvement of India in the internal affairs of the country and invited to India to terms of peace. He highlighted the international negation about the problems of Pakistan regarding the conspiracy of India against Pakistan. The concordance of word India can be seen that highlights the involvement of India in personal affairs of Pakistan and also their militant behavior against Pakistan.

File	Left Context	Hit	Right Context
1 akistani Foreign...	sleep in the streets of Calcutta. The people of West	Bengal	are the poorest. India goes hat in hand to
2 akistani Foreign...	there be a republic of Texas. We did not buy	Bengal	as Alaska was bought by the United States. We
3 akistani Foreign...	injustice and exploitation, when the parlia mentary rule in West	Bengal	has been superseded by presidential rule? Is India going
4 akistani Foreign...	going to impose presidential-rule in West Bengal, in their	Bengal,	how can they do any better in our Bengal?
5 akistani Foreign...	If they are going to impose presidential-rule in West	Bengal,	in their Bengal, how can they do any better
6 akistani Foreign...	on he corrected himself to say that the population of	Bengal-	of Muslim Bengal-was 76 million. If he had waited
7 akistani Foreign...	it going to give when its own people in Western	Bengal	sleep in the streets, where there is terrible poverty,
8 akistani Foreign...	India going to do better for East Pakistan, for Muslim	Bengal,	than it has done for West Bengal? Thousands of
9 akistani Foreign...	stays there, it will be a grim reminder for Muslim	Bengal	that they are under Hindu occupation, and you will
10 akistani Foreign...	their Bengal, how can they do any better in our	Bengal?	They will not. And time will show that they
11 akistani Foreign...	Pakistan, for Muslim Bengal, than it has done for West	Bengal?	Thousands of West Bengali people sleep in the streets
12 akistani Foreign...	should appreciate the position taken by their Government. Muslim	Bengal	was a part of Pakistan of its free will,
13 akistani Foreign...	himself to say that the population of Bengal-of Muslim	Bengal-	was 76 million. If he had waited for a few

Figure 4 Concordance Results of Bhutto's speech

The issue of Bengal was the major theme of Bhutto's speech at UNGA. He reminded the united nation again and again the problems of Bengal and also gave the solution of their problems. He highlighted and exposed the conspiracy of India to separate East Pakistan with the name of Bengal. He highlighted the miserable condition of Bengal people and stressed the solution of Bengal with terms of peace by uplifting the Indian control and conspiracy against Bengal.

File	Left Context	Hit	Right Context
1 akistani Foreign...	India talks about the will of the people of East	Pakistan	and claims that it had to attack Pakistan in
2 akistani Foreign...	victory than the victory that Mujibur Rahman received in East	Pakistan,	and he should have taken cognizance of that. But
3 akistani Foreign...	Government has acted according to its great traditions by supporting	Pakistan,	and I. will go to the people of the
4 akistani Foreign...	events. There is a lot of goodwill for France in	Pakistan,	and they will not get the same goodwill in
5 akistani Foreign...	for this reason. I was needed by the people of	Pakistan,	and when I was leaving Pakistan I. was in
6 akistani Foreign...	which are rooted in historic principles. The principle is that	Pakistan	is an indepen dent, sovereign state which came into
7 akistani Foreign...	East Pakistan, then what has it done about Kashmir? East	Pakistan	is an integral part of Pakistan. Kashmir is a
8 akistani Foreign...	sessions before. The time has come when, as far as	Pakistan	is concerned, we shall have to speak the truth
9 akistani Foreign...	if our state is obliterated? We will build a new	Pakistan.	We will build a better Pakistan. We will build
10 akistani Foreign...	will build a new Pakistan. We will build a better	Pakistan.	We will build a greater Pakistan. The Security Council
11 akistani Foreign...	shall you reap. Remember that Biblical saying. Today, it is	Pakistan.	We are your guinea pigs today. But there will
12 akistani Foreign...	Madison. Hamilton, right down to Roosevelt and Wilson by supporting	Pakistan	as an independent state, its national integrity and its
13 akistani Foreign...	India thinks that it is going to subjugate Pakistan, Eastern	Pakistan	as well as Western Pakistan-because we are one
14 akistani Foreign...	and they will not get the same goodwill in East	Pakistan	because in East Pakistan already the clock is now
15 akistani Foreign...	going to subjugate Pakistan, Eastern Pakistan as well as Western	Pakistan-	because we are one people, we are one state-
16 akistani Foreign...	because my party emerged as the strongest party in West	Pakistan.	But here was an international poll and India flouted
17 akistani Foreign...	relations. A new chapter may have begun in India and	Pakistan	but please do not start a new dreadful chapter

Figure 5 Concordance Results of Bhutto's speech

File	Left Context	Hit	Right Context
1 akistani Foreign...	half of China. That was the reality. Since the Opium	War,	China has seen reality. The reality for France was
2 akistani Foreign...	so. But as it was said about the 1967 Arab-Israel	war,	the military victory of Israel made it more difficult
3 akistani Foreign...	President Woodrow Wilson said that he fought the First World	War	to end wars for all time. The League of

Figure 6 Concordance Results of Bhutto's speech

The above figures show concordance the concordance of Pakistan and war. Bhutto attracted the attention of international organizations to major problems faced by Pakistan concerning with the Bengal. He also highlighted the miserable condition of people of East Pakistan. He highlighted that east Pakistan is integral part of Pakistan and stressed the neglected behavior of United Nations regarding Bengal and Kashmir as well. He warned the international community by the

threats of war by giving the examples of many countries that involved in war. He stressed on the solution through treaty and terms of peace.

IMRAN KHAN

Pakistan	29
India	27
Muslim	13
Rss	13
Islam	12
Change	10
Developing	10
Leaders	10
Political	10
Prophet	10
Islamophobia	9
Kashmiri	9
Kashmiris	9
Pbuh	9
Climate	9
Community	9
Modi	8

Figure 7 Table of major themes in Imran Khan's speeches

The above table presents major themes in Imran Khan's two speeches at UNGA. A. Pakistan and India

1. Key Themes and Issues

A. Pakistan (29 occurrences) and India (27 occurrences) are the most frequently used words, emphasizing the centrality of the Pakistan-India conflict in Imran Khan's speeches. Imran Khan has repeatedly raised concerns about India's actions, particularly in relation to the situation in Jammu and Kashmir, where the political climate was increasingly volatile. These frequent mentions show that the Pakistan-India dispute was a central issue that he sought to address on the international stage.

B. Islam and Muslim Issues

Muslim (13 occurrences) and Islam (12 occurrences) reflect Imran Khan's emphasis on the global Muslim community and the challenges they face. The use of these terms aligns with his broader rhetoric of presenting Islam as a key factor in addressing global issues. This is particularly significant in the context of rising Islamophobia, a theme that will be explored below.

C. RSS and Islamophobia

The term RSS (13 occurrences) refers to the Rashtriya Swayamsevak Sangh, a Hindu nationalist

organization in India. Imran Khan has criticized the RSS for its role in exacerbating tensions between India and Pakistan, particularly through its influence on the Indian government and the treatment of Muslims in India. This term is crucial in highlighting his concerns about the growing religious extremism in India.

Islamophobia (9 occurrences) points to Khan's critique of rising anti-Muslim sentiment globally, and particularly in India. The frequent use of this term signals his strong position on the need to address discrimination against Muslims, both within India and on the international stage.

D. Kashmir and Kashmiris

Kashmiri (9 occurrences) and Kashmiris (9 occurrences) are central to Imran Khan's speeches, underlining the importance of the Kashmir conflict in his address to the UNGA. Khan has consistently highlighted the suffering of Kashmiri Muslims under Indian rule, framing the issue as one of self-determination, human rights, and justice for the Kashmiri people.

E. Leadership and Political Change

Leaders (10 occurrences) and Political (10 occurrences) reflect Imran Khan's broader discourse on the need for leadership that promotes peace, justice, and equality. His speeches often touch on global governance issues, urging world leaders to take a stand on human rights and the treatment of marginalized communities, especially Muslims in India and Kashmir.

F. Climate Change

Climate (9 occurrences) highlights Imran Khan's efforts to address the global environmental crisis. In his UNGA speeches, Khan has called for collective action to combat climate change, particularly focusing on its impact on developing countries like Pakistan, which are disproportionately affected by climate-related disasters.

G. Modi

The word Modi (8 occurrences) refers to Indian Prime Minister Narendra Modi. Imran Khan has frequently criticized Modi's policies, especially in relation to Kashmir and his treatment of Muslims. By mentioning Modi, Khan draws attention to the role of leadership in exacerbating regional tensions and human rights abuses.

2. Analysis of Language Use and Rhetorical Strategies

Imran Khan's frequent use of terms like Pakistan, India, Kashmir, Muslim, and Islamophobia suggests that his primary aim was to draw attention to the plight of Muslims in India and Kashmir, and to rally the international community to take a stronger stance on these issues. His choice of words reflects a focus on justice, human rights, and the need for political change.

The repeated use of terms such as RSS and Modi highlights Khan's critique of Hindu nationalism and the policies of the Indian government under Modi's leadership. By using these terms, Khan positioned India as an aggressor, particularly in the context of Kashmir, and called for international intervention to resolve the ongoing crisis.

Khan's frequent mention of climate further emphasizes his agenda of promoting global cooperation on environmental issues, especially in developing nations that are vulnerable to the effects of climate change. His emphasis on leaders and political change underlines his call for

more responsible leadership in addressing both geopolitical and global challenges.

Finally, terms such as Muslim, Islamophobia, and Prophet reflect Khan's broader concern with global religious tensions, framing the treatment of Muslims as a critical issue in international diplomacy.

File	Left Context	Hit	Right Context
1 Statement by t...	This Assembly should declare an "International Day to Combat	Islamophobia"	and build a coalition to fight this scourge - scourge
2 General ...	lions Muslims in the world. Muslims living across all continents.	Islamophobia	has grown since 9/11 and it is alarming. It is
3 General ...	that is the Islam of Prophet (PBUH). Why is there	Islamophobia?	How will an average American differentiate between a moderate
4 General ...	Most important thing I want to say, to explain this	Islamophobia,	I've played cricket in the West & I know
5 General ...	how the western mind works. One of the reasons for	Islamophobia;	in 1989 this book was published maligning, ridiculing our Proph
6 Statement by t...	today where, I am sad to say, the state sponsors	Islamophobia,	is India. The reason behind this is RSS ideology
7 Statement by t...	minorities in several places. These trends have also accentuated '	Islamophobia'.	Muslims continue to be targeted with impunity in many
8 General ...	a way to stop this plunder. My third point is	Islamophobia;	there are 1.3 billion Muslims in the world. Muslims living
9 General ...	has nothing to do with our religion. We have faced	Islamophobia	while travelling abroad; and in European countries it is

Figure 8 Concordance Results of word 'Islamophobia' in Imran Khan's speech

In both of his speeches, he spoke of Islam and Islamophobia. He discussed Islam and highlighted the issue of Islamophobia with much more explanation in order to inform the world about the emotions, feelings, and love of Muslims for their religion. The context of the discussion on Islam and Islamophobia is vivid in the concordance of the above-mentioned words in the pictures. He talked about the misrepresentation of Islam and how it is illogically linked to terrorism. He also discussed that there is no radical Islam, that there is only one Islam, and that is the Islam of the Prophet Muhammad PBUH. The concept of radical Islam was created in the West after the 9/11 attack. He also discussed the fact that people in the West do not know about actual Islam, and the propaganda against Islam is alarming. The fear of Islam

File	Left Context	Hit	Right Context
1 Statement by t...	gross human rights violations, and agree to resolve the Jammu &	Kashmir	dispute in accordance with the relevant UN Security Council
2 Statement by t...	peace and stability in South Asia until the Jammu and	Kashmir	dispute is resolved on the basis of international legitimacy.
3 Statement by t...	resident, For over 72 years, India has illegally occupied Jammu and	Kashmir	against the wishes of the Kashmiri people, and in
4 General ...	Kashmir special status. They escalated the number of troops in	Kashmir	and put 8 million people under curfew. Mr. President; I
5 General ...	lifted? Modi says this is done for the prosperity of	Kashmir.	But what will happen when 8 million Kashmiris come out
6 Statement by t...	ashmir dispute is resolved on the basis of international legitimacy.	Kashmir	has been rightly described as a "nuclear flash point".
7 Statement by t...	its illegal actions and atrocities in Indian Occupied Jammu and	Kashmir,	India is playing a dangerous game of upping the
8 General ...	any atrocities in the Muslim world? I picture myself in	Kashmir,	locked up for 50 days. Hearing about rapes, the Indian
9 Statement by t...	resolutions and of course the wishes of the people of	Kashmir.	Mr. President, Pakistan's desire for peace in our
10 Statement by t...	Council and indeed its own commitments to the people of	Kashmir.	On 5th August last year, India illegally and unilaterally
11 General ...	for the United Nations. You are the one who said	Kashmir	right to self determination. This is not the time
12 General ...	this is the time when the UN must insist on	Kashmir'	s right to self determination!
13 General ...	the revocation of the article 370 happened which used to give	Kashmir	special status. They escalated the number of troops in
14 General ...	be another Pulwama incident because of their own cruelty in	Kashmir,	they will blame us and try to bomb us
15 Statement by t...	Timor. The Council has considered the situation in Jammu and	Kashmir	three times in the past year. It must take
16 Statement by t...	regime has itself called the 'Final Solution' for Jammu and	Kashmir.	To this end, the military siege is being followed
17 General ...	ask. Now I want to move on to talk about	Kashmir.	When we came into power, my first priority was

Figure 9 Concordance Results of word 'Kashmir' in Imran Khan's speeches

The issue of Kashmir was at the heart of both speeches, and both the speeches addressed the

issue with more energy, faith, and boldness. He reminded the United Nations of the Kashmir resolution. He spoke openly about the brutality and cruelty of the Indian government and its army. The unceasing and inhuman curfew of the occupied Indian Kashmir was severely condemned. He stressed the solution of the Kashmir issue and warned the United Nations of its deteriorating situation and its consequences. The main aim was to pressurize India to lift the inhuman curfew and give Kashmiris a right of self-determination. The greater frequency of words related to Kashmir in both the speeches demonstrates the seriousness of the Prime Minister of Pakistan, Imran Khan.

File	Left Context	Hit	Right Context
1 General ...	UN reported on this. But the world did nothing & sees	India	as a huge market. Materialism has trumped humanity. What
2 General ...	t you think that 180 Million Muslims will be radicalised in	India	as they see 8 million Kashmiris locked up? And what
3 Statement by t...	and this does not augur well for the future of	India	as we all know that marginalization of human beings
4 General ...	& mantra of Islamic terrorism. The phrase Islamic terrorism allows	India	to dismiss human rights and further increase cruelty on
5 General ...	on an Indian convoy. Immediately India blamed Pakistan. I told	India	to give us any proof and we'd act.
6 General ...	is the time when you, the United Nations, must urge	India	to lift the curfew; to free the 13,000 Kashmiris who
7 Statement by t...	to a lesser extent towards the Christians. They believe that	India	is exclusively for Hindus and others are not equal
8 Statement by t...	gal actions and atrocities in Indian Occupied Jammu and Kashmir,	India	is playing a dangerous game of upping the military
9 Statement by t...	India. My parents, Mr. President, were born in the colonial	India	and I was the first generation that grew up
10 General ...	And then India; let me tell you my relationship with	India.	Because of cricket, which is followed with great passion
11 General ...	Indian forces blew himself up on an Indian convoy. Immediately	India	blamed Pakistan. I told India to give us any
12 Statement by t...	ings leads to their radicalization. Mr. President, For over 72 years,	India	has illegally occupied Jammu and Kashmir against the wishes
13 General ...	great passion in the subcontinent, I have great friends in	India.	I've always loved going to India. So my
14 Statement by t...	to the people of Kashmir. On 5th August last year,	India	illegally and unilaterally sought to change the status of
15 General ...	a decision taken by all political parties. I know that	India	keeps saying we have militant organisations but I invite
16 General ...	ed mending fences. We engaged with Afghanistan, Iran. And then	India;	let me tell you my relationship with India. Because
17 Statement by t...	has always called for a peaceful solution. To this end,	India	must rescind the measures it has instituted since 5 August 2019,

File	Left Context	Hit	Right Context
1 General ...	the RSS is. Mr Modi is a "life member" of	RSS.	An organisation inspired by Hitler and Mussolini. They believed
2 Statement by t...	Minister Modi; and in 2007, over 50 Muslims were burnt alive by	RSS	arsonists aboard the Samjhota Express Train. In Assam, around
3 General ...	the supremacy of the Aryan race. This is open knowledge.	RSS	believes in the racial superiority of Hindus. It was
4 Statement by t...	objective of this brutal campaign is to impose what the	RSS-	BJP regime has itself called the 'Final Solution' for
5 General ...	party gave a statement that terrorists were being trained in	RSS	Camps. Modi was not allowed to travel to the
6 Statement by t...	ansing India's 200 million Muslims and other minorities. In 1992, the	RSS	destroyed the Babri Mosque; in 2002, some 2000 Muslims were slaug
7 Statement by t...	While the Nazis hate was directed at the Jews, the	RSS	directs it towards the Muslims and to a lesser
8 Statement by t...	India today. This extremist ideology was founded in 1920s. The	RSS	founding fathers were inspired by the Nazis and they
9 General ...	logy of hate murdered Mahatma Gandhi. The hate ideology allowed	RSS	goons under Modi's CM ship in Gujarat to
10 Statement by t...	state sponsors Islamophobia, is India. The reason behind this is	RSS	ideology that unfortunately rules India today. This extremist ideolog
11 General ...	under curfew. Mr.President; I have to explain what the	RSS	is. Mr Modi is a "life member" of RSS.
12 Statement by t...	make it clear that any attempt by the fascist totalitarian	RSS-	led Indian government to aggress against Pakistan will be
13 General ...	You can all just google the founding fathers of the	RSS	like Golwalkar. This ideology of hate murdered Mahatma Gandhi.

Figure 10 Concordance Results Imran Khan's speeches

File	Left Context	Hit	Right Context
1 General ...	be locked up. These are humans. Arrogance has blinded PM	Modi	and BJP. This racial superiority; what does he think
2 Statement by t...	Gujarat, and this was under the watch of Chief Minister	Modi;	and in 2007, over 50 Muslims were burnt alive by RSS
3 General ...	India. So my first move was to reach out to	Modi &	I said let's work our differences, leave our
4 General ...	President; I have to explain what the RSS is. Mr	Modi	is a "life member" of RSS. An organisation inspired
5 General ...	ered Mahatma Gandhi. The hate ideology allowed RSS goons under	Modi'	s CM ship in Gujarat to butcher 2000 Muslims. The
6 General ...	trumped humanity. What will happen when the curfew is lifted?	Modi	says this is done for the prosperity of Kashmir.
7 General ...	want the situation to escalate. In the election campaign, Mr.	Modi	used terms like "This was just a trailer. The
8 General ...	a statement that terrorists were being trained in RSS Camps.	Modi	was not allowed to travel to the US. What

Figure 11: Concordance Resultsof word 'modi' in Imran Khan's speeches

The greater portions of both the speeches were specified for India, Modi, and RSS. Imran Khan

openly criticized the Modi led government for its treacherous activities against Pakistan. He discussed the role of India in destabilizing the peace in the region, the Hindutva ideology, and the heinous role of RSS in conspiring against peace. The sufferings of Muslims in the Modi-led government were also highlighted. The Gujarat incident and the abominable incident of Babri masjid were among the long list of RSS's heinous acts. The Modi led government was compared to that of Nazis, and the similarities between Modi and Hitler were also elucidated. The role of RSS and Modi relation with it were questioned and brought to the notice of the international community. Apart from Muslims, the problems faced by Christians in the Modi led government was also discussed.

File	Left Context	Hit	Right Context
1 Statement by t...	firm our support for multilateralism. Mr. President, The COVID-19	pandemic	has illustrated the oneness of humanity. In our interconnected
2 Statement by t...	safe unless everyone is safe. Locking down to control the	pandemic	has triggered the worst recession since the Great Depression
3 Statement by t...	among the success stories in controlling and responding to the	pandemic.	However, we are still not out of the woods,
4 Statement by t...	to mitigating the effects of climate change. Mr. President, The	pandemic	was an opportunity to bring humanity together. Unfortunately, it

Figure 12: concordance of words "climate change" in both the speeches

File	Left Context	Hit	Right Context
1 General ...	should be our people as we have similar problems; poverty &	climate change.	Highest number of people reside in subcontinent. On
2 Statement by t...	must again reiterate the threat posed to mankind due to	Climate Change.	Unprecedented fires in Australia, Siberia, California, Brazil; unpr
3 General ...	is among the top 10 nations in the world affected by	climate change.	We depend on or rivers, we are mainly
4 Statement by t...	but it is one of those countries most affected by	climate change.	Yet, we have decided to take the lead
5 Statement by t...	have decided to take the lead as we consider addressing	climate change	a universal responsibility. We have launched an extremely
6 Statement by t...	this is because of the increased threat of nuclear war,	Climate Change,	and sadly the rise of authoritarian regimes. We
7 Statement by t...	three years as our contribution to mitigating the effects of	climate change.	Mr. President, The pandemic was an opportunity to
8 General ...	that the world must address. First let me talk about	climate change;	I have seen a lot of leaders talk

Figure 13: concordance of the word "Pandemic" in the Imran khan's speech.

The figures above show the concordance of words like climate change and pandemics. In both his speeches, he spoke about the impact of climate change on the world as well as on Pakistan. He discussed his government's efforts to address climate change issues such as reforestation in the province of KP. In addition, in his second speech, he discussed the issue of COVID 19, the pandemic. In his first speech, he did not discuss the issue of the pandemic since there was no pandemic at that time. He informed the international community about his country's efforts to combat the pandemic and asked them to help the poor countries during the pandemic.

File	Left Context	Hit	Right Context
1 General ...	b/c of Muslim rule. They openly stated hatred for	Muslims	and Christians. This is all open knowledge. You can
2 Statement by t...	Hindu Rashtra by subjugating, even cleansing India's 200 million	Muslims	and other minorities. In 1992, the RSS destroyed the Babri
3 Statement by t...	directed at the Jews, the RSS directs it towards the	Muslims	and to a lesser extent towards the Christians. They
4 Statement by t...	under the watch of Chief Minister Modi; and in 2007, over 50	Muslims	were burnt alive by RSS arsonists aboard the Samjhota
5 Statement by t...	concentration camps being filled with by Muslim Indian citizens.	Muslims	were falsely blamed, vilified and victimized for spreading the
6 Statement by t...	. In 1992, the RSS destroyed the Babri Mosque; in 2002, some 2000	Muslims	were slaughtered in Gujarat, and this was under the
7 General ...	intolerant. I blame some people in the West who provoked	Muslims.	But this is where majority of the Muslim leaders
8 Statement by t...	ideology is set to marginalize almost 300 million human beings -	Muslims,	Christians and Sikhs. This is unprecedented in history and
9 General ...	the racial superiority of Hindus. It was hatred for the	Muslims &	Christians. They believe that the golden age of Hinduism
10 Statement by t...	everal places. These trends have also accentuated 'Islamophobia'.	Muslims	continue to be targeted with impunity in many countries.
11 Statement by t...	aboard the Samjhota Express Train. In Assam, around two million	Muslims	face the prospects of being arbitrarily stripped of their
12 Statement by t...	vw vigilantes attack and kill Muslims with impunity. Last February,	Muslims	faced targeted killings, with police complicity in New Delhi.
13 General ...	watching this knowing that this is only happening to Kashmiri	Muslims.	How would the Jewish community react if even 8000 Jews
14 General ...	this plunder. My third point is Islamophobia; there are 1.3 billion	Muslims	in the world. Muslims living across all continents. Islamophobia
15 General ...	point is Islamophobia; there are 1.3 billion Muslims in the world.	Muslims	living across all continents. Islamophobia has grown since 9/11 an
16 General ...	goons under Modi's CM ship in Gujarat to butcher 2000	Muslims.	The Congress party gave a statement that terrorists were
17 General ...	hey see 8 million Kashmiris locked up? And what about 1.3 billion	Muslims	who are watching this knowing that this is only

	File	Left Context	Hit	Right Context
1	Statement by t...	office, our consistent effort has been to fundamentally transform	Pakistan.	We envisage 'Naya Pakistan' to be modeled on the
2	General ...	are facing a huge catastrophe. In KP, a province of	Pakistan,	we planted a billion trees in 5 years. Now we
3	Statement by t...	as well as the poor in all the countries. In	Pakistan,	we realized very early on that if we imposed
4	General ...	that there is no such thing as radical Islam. In	Pakistan;	we were the eye of the storm & our govt
5	General ...	ng His Excellency Imran Khan, Prime Minister, Islamic Republic of	Pakistan	I stand here at this forum of world leaders
6	General ...	blew himself up on an Indian convoy. Immediately India blamed	Pakistan.	I told India to give us any proof and
7	Statement by t...	was the first generation that grew up in an independent	Pakistan.	I want to make it clear that any attempt
8	Statement by t...	mmitment to mobilize US\$ 100 billion annually as climate finance.	Pakistan'	s contribution to carbon emissions is minimal, but it
9	Statement by t...	course the wishes of the people of Kashmir. Mr. President,	Pakistan'	s desire for peace in our region is also
10	Statement by t...	from the worst fall out of the lock down. Today,	Pakistan'	s response is cited among the success stories in
11	General ...	to radicalisation. This is one of the most critical times.	Pakistan	will be blamed should something happen. Two nuclear armed
12	Statement by t...	e fascist totalitarian RSS-led Indian government to aggress against	Pakistan	will be met by a nation that will fight
13	Statement by t...	te greater democracy, accountability, transparency and efficiency.	Pakistan	will continue to participate actively in this process and
14	Statement by t...	to protect the Kashmiris from an impending genocide by India.	Pakistan	has always called for a peaceful solution. To this
15	Statement by t...	of Control and the Working Boundary targeting innocent civilians,	Pakistan	has exercised maximum restraint. We have consistently sensitized t
16	General ...	but as they say, ideas without funding is mere hallucination.	Pakistan	is among the top 10 nations in the world affected
17	Statement by t...	minated in the U.S.-Taliban Peace Agreement on 29 February 2020.	Pakistan	is deeply gratified that it has fulfilled its part

	File	Left Context	Hit	Right Context
1	General ...	humans were equal; whatever the colour of their skin. The	Prophet (PBUH) announced that one of the greatest deeds is
2	General ...	the witness to our Divine book, the Holy Quran. The	Prophet (PBUH) is the ideal we want to live up
3	General ...	it is going against the teachings of our religion. Our	Prophet (PBUH) lives in our heart, and when he is
4	General ...	of the Muslim leaders let the Muslim community down. Our	Prophet (PBUH) was the witness to our Divine book, the
5	General ...	phobia; in 1989 this book was published maligning, ridiculing our	Prophet (PBUH). The west could not understand what was the
6	General ...	is only ONE Islam and that is the Islam of	Prophet (PBUH). Why is there Islamophobia? How will an average
7	Statement by t...	principles of the State of Madinah, established by our Holy	Prophet	Muhammad (PBUH). A just and humane society where all
8	General ...	ame a watershed. And every 2-3 years someone would malign our	Prophet (PBUH), Muslims would react, and the west would term
9	General ...	for; do not hurt our sentiments by maligning our Holy	Prophet (PBUH). That is all we ask. Now I want
10	Statement by t...	impunity in many countries. Our shrines are being destroyed; our	Prophet (Peace Be Upon Him) insulted; the Holy Quran burnt -

	File	Left Context	Hit	Right Context
1	Statement by t...	the world that can help us achieve our goals of	peace	and stability in our neighbourhood. This is also a
2	Statement by t...	to the end. Mr. President, There will be no durable	peace	and stability in South Asia until the Jammu and
3	Statement by t...	s" - within and outside Afghanistan - to subvert the peace process.	Peace	and stability in Afghanistan will open new opportunities for
4	Statement by t...	for collective action - in managing international conflicts, fostering	peace	and security, promoting equitable development and addressing glo
5	Statement by t...	outlawed and equitable prosperity for all pursued in conditions of	peace	and security. I thank you.
6	Statement by t...	equitable dispensation. To achieve this goal, we need to have	peace	and stability. Thus our foreign policy aims to have
7	Statement by t...	the people of Kashmir. Mr. President, Pakistan's desire for	peace	in our region is also manifest in our efforts
8	Statement by t...	seize this historic opportunity to achieve reconciliation and restore	peace	in their war-torn country. Through the Intra-Afghan
9	Statement by t...	facilitated the process that culminated in the U.S.-Taliban	Peace	Agreement on 29 February 2020. Pakistan is deeply gratified that it
10	Statement by t...	in many countries. Our shrines are being destroyed; our Prophet (Peace	Be Upon Him) insulted; the Holy Quran burnt - and
11	General ...	people of Kashmir. Why would we ever want to disrupt	peace?	But it's because there is no other narrative
12	General ...	be that country that would try its best to bring	peace.	Joining the war on terror, Pakistan went through one
13	Statement by t...	o allow "spoilers" - within and outside Afghanistan - to subvert the	peace	process. Peace and stability in Afghanistan will open new
14	Statement by t...	onditions on the Palestinian people especially in Gaza cannot bring	peace	to a troubled region. Pakistan continues to support a
15	Statement by t...	peace and stability. Thus our foreign policy aims to have	peace	with our neighbours and settle disputes through dialogue. Mr.

File	Left Context	Hit	Right Context
General ...	will FIGHT! I am not threatening here about a nuclear	war;	it is a worry. It is a test for
Statement by t...	part of this political solution. After almost two decades of	war,	it is imperative not to allow "spoilers" - within and
General ...	the war, 150 billion dollar to our economy. We joined the	war	against the Soviets in the 1980's. Pakistan trained the
General ...	My point here is that we must address this. Post 9/11,	war	against "radical Islam" started, rather than Muslim leaders trying
General ...	one of its worst periods. We lost 70,000 people to the	war, 150	billion dollar to our economy. We joined the war
Statement by t...	and this is because of the increased threat of nuclear	war,	Climate Change, and sadly the rise of authoritarian regimes.
Statement by t...	ention. Changing demographic structure of occupied territory is a	war	crime. Mr. President, The brave Kashmiri people will never
General ...	that would try its best to bring peace. Joining the	war	on terror, Pakistan went through one of its worst
General ...	turned against us 70,000 Pakistanis lost their lives, due to a	war	Pakistan had nothing to do with. No Pakistani was
General ...	it stand up for justice and humanity? If a conventional	war	starts between 2 countries, nuclear countries anything could happ
Statement by t...	ric opportunity to achieve reconciliation and restore peace in their	war-	torn country. Through the Intra-Afghan Negotiations that comm

Figure 14: concordance analysis of Imran khan's speeches

The above concordance analysis demonstrates major themes and issues that were highlighted in UNGA. Imran Khan highlighted how the Muslims are targeted under the mask of Islamophobia. He also stressed how the Muslims are treated in India. He unveiled the mask of RSS in India against Muslims. He exposed the agenda of RSS and typical Hindus against the Muslims. He referred to the Babri attack and treatment with the Muslims in India. He also highlighted the issues of Kashmiris. He also highlighted the role of Pakistan for peace process in the territory. He drew the attention of world leaders to the problems and issues faced by Pakistan and also demonstrated the role of Pakistan for climate change. He made them realize there is no radical Islam in Pakistan. He discussed the initiatives taken by his party to make Pakistan prosperous and peaceful.

He strongly condemned the world behavior against the Holy Prophet (PBUH). He condemned the ridiculing of Westerners against the Holy Prophet (PBUH). He made them realize the Prophet (PBUH) lives in our hearts. He is the witness of our Divine book, who ridicules Him, hurts our souls deeply. There is no radical Islam. There is only one Islam that is Islam of the Prophet (PBUH) who set the example in the state of Madina that is an ideal state for the whole world with respect to moral values and democratic state.

Imran Khan stressed peace in his speech for the prosperity of the whole territory. He used the word peace with stability 6 times in the above concordance that how much peace and stability is mandatory not only for Pakistan but for the whole territory.

He highlighted the damage faced by Pakistan in wars. He demonstrated how much lives as well as wealth were lost in these wars. He pointed to the threats and after-effects of war. He also stressed to stop the war against innocent Kashmiris. He made the world leaders realize to pay heed to justice and humanity.

5. CONCLUSION

The contents of the two speeches were to a great extent important but their themes were different. There is similarity of passion and style of speech but themes are different. One thing

that makes the speeches different is the use of frequency of the words which shows the focus and the seriousness of the issues highlighted. Imran spoke about Kashmir, the role of the RSS, Modi, the Indian Government, Islam, Islamophobia, and climate change in both speeches. On the other hand, Bhutto discussed the issues of Bengal, the neglected behavior of United Nations for Pakistan against the Indian Conspiracy. Issues of war, India are the same that were discussed by both leaders in UNGA. In speeches of both leaders, the frequently used words are shown in the graphs given above in the data analysis section. Some of the words that were commonly used were Islam, Islamophobia, Kashmir, India, Modi, RSS, ideology, Hindutva, climate change, corruption, money laundering, pandemics, Bengal, Muslims of Bengal and Soviet Union.

The issue of Kashmir had substantial space in the speeches of both leaders and spoke eloquently about the sufferings of Kashmiri people and the atrocities committed by Indian forces. In speeches of both leaders, they appealed to the international community to do something for peace and dialogue in territory. He also told the international community to take the issue of climate change seriously and to play their part in solving the problem. Additionally, Imran Khan, Pakistan's prime minister, spoke openly about Islamophobia and its impact on Muslims around the world. Bhutto highlighted the issue of Kashmir and unveiled the mask of conspiracy of India against Pakistan. Bhutto's aim was to make the world realize that peace in territory was necessary and the role of United Nations is mandatory to resolve the issue of Pakistan against India. Imran's main aim was to let the world know the true Islam and the love of the Muslims for their religion and their prophet.

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